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Uncommon primary presentation of multiple endocrine neoplasia – case report

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Introduction: Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN 1) is a syndrome characterized by neoplasia involving the parathyroid glands, enteropancreatic tumors, anterior pituitary adenoma and other neuroendocrine tumors with variable penetrance. MEN 1 has estimated prevalence of 2 – 20 per 100 000 in the general population. Although the most commonly involved gland is the parathyroid gland, the variable penetrance of several neoplastic components can make the differential diagnosis and treatment challenging. We report herein the case of MEN 1 based on clinical, biochemical and pathological studies.

Case: The patient was a 49-year-old woman, who presented with acromegaly caused by pituitary adenoma. She underwent transsphenoidal resection of adenoma and was on bromokriptin therapy. After six years she was admitted to hospital because of reevaluation of active acromegaly. In further diagnostics there were found elevated PTH level (125.8 pg/ml) with normal ionized calcium levels and slightly elevated bone turnover markers and euthyroid nodular goiter. Dual phase parathyroid scintigraphy with ^{99m}Tc-MIBI showed adenoma of right superior parathyroid gland and hot nodule in left lobe of thyroid gland. She underwent parathyroidectomy due to enlarged right superior parathyroid gland that was shown histologically to be a parathyroid adenoma.

Conclusion: Although MEN 1 syndrome is most commonly primarily presented as hyperparathyroidism, patients with pituitary adenoma as potential presentations of MEN 1, should be monitored to prevent complications of developed syndrome.

Key words: Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia Type 1

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Separation of strontium and yttrium by supported liquid membrane extraction

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Introduction: Radionuclide ⁹⁰Y is one of the most suitable radionuclide for the radiotherapy of solid and non-operable malignant tumors. ⁹⁰Sr is an ideal source for obtaining carrier-free ⁹⁰Y. The aim of the present study was to investigate the separation of Y(III) from Sr(II) by supported liquid membrane extraction (SLME) in a hollow-fibre contactor under continuous mode of operation and using di(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (DEHPA) as a carrier in the organic phase.

Methods: The SLME was performed in hollow fiber contactor containing polypropylene hollow fibers. The donor solution (25 mL of 500 ppm Sr(II) and 20 ppm Y(III) in 0.1 M HCl) was fed along the shell side of contactor in a recirculated mode of operation by a peristaltic pump (4.5 ml/min). The acceptor solution (4 mL of 3 M HCl) was fed along the lumen of the hollow fiber in a recirculated mode of operation by a peristaltic pump (0.8 ml/min). The concentrations of both metal ions were determined in donor and acceptor by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) solutions during the extraction which lasted 6 hrs.

Results: It was found that separation factor (α) depends on pH of aqueous solution, DEHPA concentration, and the organic solvent. The highest α (82900) was obtained from aqueous solution pH 1 (0.1 M HCl) and 15% DEHPA in n-dodecane.

The removal efficiency (R) of Y(III) increases during the SLME and reached the maximum of 85%. The extraction efficiency (E) of Y(III) also reised during the SLME, and after 6 hrs of extraction E is 60%. It means that 25% of extracted Y(III) was captured in the membrane. The changing of Sr(II) concentration in the donor solution was not observed. Also, Sr(II) was not detected in the acceptor phase.

Conclusion: The obtained results show that SLME is an effective method for separation Y(III) from Sr(II) and for obtaining carrier-free Y(III). The method described in this paper can be used for obtaining yttrium, suitable for therapeutic use in the treatment of non-operating tumors.

Key words: Pharmaceuticals Preparation; Radioisotopes; Strontium; Yttrium; Liquid-Liquid Extraction; Membranes, Artificial; Spectrophotometry, Atomic